

1-Isonicotinoyl-2-salicylidenehydrazine as a Metallochromic Indicator for Iron

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In an earlier paper¹, 1-isonicotinoyl-2-salicylidenehydrazine was suggested as a potential complex former. The disappearance of its deep brown Fe (III) complex has been utilised to mark the end point in the titrimetric determination of Fe(III) against EDTA.

Stock solutions of ferric ammonium sulphate and EDTA were prepared from E. Merck (G.R.) grade reagents; the former was standardised by complexometric titration². The solutions of other cations and buffers (sodium acetate and HCl) were prepared from A.R. grade reagents. 0.1% Solutions of 1-isonicotinoyl-2-salicylidenehydrazine (5 ml) in 95% ethanol were used as the indicator.

Procedure.—Ferric ammonium sulphate (10 ml) was taken in a 250-ml Erlenmeyer flask. The pH of the solution was adjusted between 2.2 and 2.5, which was found to be the most sensitive range for the sharp end point. The solution was then diluted to 50ml, followed by the addition of the indicator solution (5ml). It was titrated against Na-EDTA till the brown colour changed to a very light yellow one. Although the indicator is sparingly soluble in water, its Fe (III) complex is highly soluble.

The studies at different pH in the range of 1-3 showed that sharpest colour change took place between pH 2.2 and 2.5. At pH values lower than 2.0, the end point was not sharp, whereas at higher values of pH, hydrolysis of iron occurred.

The titration was carried out at different temperatures in the range of 0° to 50°. At temperatures < 10°, higher results were obtained, but the use of the range of temperature 15-50° provided accurate results.

1. Katiyar and Tandon, *Talanta*, 1964 (in press)
2. Welcher, "The Analytical Uses of Ethylenediaminetetra-acetic Acid", D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., 1958. p. 223.

The concentration of iron in the titration was varied from 0.5 mg. to 55 mg. The results obtained showed that below 1 mg. iron, the sharpness of the end point was reduced beyond identification.

Effect of Foreign Ions.—To study the interference of foreign ions, a 0.01% solution (5ml) of the cation was mixed to the fixed amount of iron and the resultant pH was adjusted between 2.2 and 2.5. The titration was carried out in the usual way.

In presence of Co^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Au^{3+} , Pd^{2+} , UO^{2+} , and Ce^{4+} , the end point was not detectable either due to formation of a precipitate or due to the dominating colour of the cation-EDTA complex. In case of Pb^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Sb^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , and Th^{4+} , higher results were obtained. Sn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , and Pt^{4+} did not interfere in the titration.

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